

Servant Leadership of School Heads: Through the Lenses of Novice Teachers

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Abstract. This study explored the teachers' perceived practice of Servant Leadership among school heads. Specifically, it aimed to answer the experiences of novice teachers regarding the servant leadership style of their School Heads and the coping mechanisms for the challenges emerging from the school heads. To achieve the objectives of the study, I made use of phenomenology. The 10 participants of this study are from Tagbaros Elementary School, Maco South District, Davao De Oro Division. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique to analyze the data. The study disclosed different themes, such as empowerment to grow professionally and strong communication; here, Principals must assist novice teachers in understanding and integrating into their work environment. By doing so, novice teachers became aware of the dynamics of the school culture and identified their ability to function as community members. Another theme was Coping with the challenges in collecting results sub-themes: Practicing mindfulness and seeking support from others; with proper training and encouragement, new teachers greatly benefit from the experience and advice their mentors have to offer. However, starting mentoring with clear guidelines and understanding the functions and roles of all parties was crucial to the level of its success. As it takes time to master the craft of teaching and develop teaching expertise, new teachers who experience a favorable mentoring period by having all the necessary elements in place can start their careers with increased confidence.

KEY WORDS

1. Novice teachers 2. devolved working conditions 3. responsibilities

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1. Introduction

Serving the school and the community is the primary responsibility of a school principal: neighborhood and broader society. Educational leadership is viewed as a service to others and offers a distinct viewpoint that highlights the values of morality and compassion. For a novice teacher, a school head practicing servant leadership is crucial because it provides a supportive, empowering environment where they feel valued, can openly ask questions, and receive tailored guidance, ultimately fostering their professional growth and increasing their confidence in the classroom, leading to better student outcomes and higher teacher retention rates. Likewise, a servant leader actively listens to novice teachers' concerns, identifies their needs, and provides targeted mentorship and professional development opportunities tailored to their chal-

allenges and encourages initiative and ownership of their teaching practices by trusting novice teachers with decision-making and giving them autonomy within their classrooms. On a global scale, Stoten (2013) suggests that investigating aspects of servant leadership can best be carried out within the frameworks of national cultural values and current practices in educational management. Similarly, Cerit (2009), who found evidence in Turkey of a positive relationship between servant leadership and job satisfaction, recommended that future studies be carried out in other countries to verify whether the results obtained in his research could be generalized. Laub (2019) proposed appreciating individuals and encouraging people, creating a sense of community, being honest, exercising leadership, and sharing leadership: People should be nurtured and valued rather than exploited for the leader's goals. Leaders recognize that people are valuable now, not simply in the future. Leaders will serve their followers by valuing people as they interact with them in organizations. They put the needs of others first, concentrating on how they may best meet those needs. Leaders are willing to put their faith in others, trust that they can perform the job, and have good intentions. When leaders pay attention to what others have to do, others will hear them if they listen without passing judgment. They pay attention because they know it is among the greatest (Laub, 2019). Lubin (2001) and Laub, 2019) emphasize that a key trait of servant leadership is prioritizing listening over speaking. Successful servant leaders are dedicated to genuinely hearing others and tuning into their intuition. They value quiet moments for reflection to gain deeper insights and personal growth. Furthermore, servant leaders are committed to developing individuals by guiding them towards reaching their full potential as both servants and leaders. They view mistakes as valuable learning opportunities and believe in each individual's inherent value and future capabilities. Provide learning opportunities and offer people opportunities for new learning. They provide an atmosphere where mistakes can lead to new insights. Leaders join them in learning and are never satisfied with the status quo. Model appropriate behavior: Leaders do not just tell others what to do. They model it for them and do it with them. They help people to develop by working alongside them so that they can learn from their example. Build up through affirmation; organizations encourage others, honor others, accept others, and build up others. They catch others doing it right. Leaders recognize accomplishments and celebrate creativity. They speak words of encouragement and intentionally affirm (Jacke, 2009). Builds Community: They desire to build community, a sense that all are part of a loving, caring team with a compelling shared vision to accomplish. Leaders know that the quality of relationships will impact people more than they will be by accomplishing tasks. Therefore, they intentionally work to build a community that works together and learns to serve one another in the process. Leaders work with people within organizations and will serve them by displaying the qualities of building community (Monarck, 2018). Fostering strong relationships is essential within any organization. Leaders and workers should be able to come together to share, listen, and reflect to build a deeper connection. Collaborative efforts should be free from unhealthy competition, with leaders setting the example by working alongside their team members genuinely and cooperatively. Leaders must appreciate and embrace diversity in ethnicity, gender, age, or culture. Taking steps to identify and challenge personal biases helps ensure everyone feels equally respected and valued within the team. To cultivate trust and respect, leaders must prioritize authenticity by being transparent, approachable, and accountable in their interactions with others. By embodying these qualities, leaders can effectively serve and support

their team members while fostering a culture of openness and honesty within the organization (Alderfer, 2009). Open and accountable Leaders will resist the tendency to protect themselves at all costs. When they make mistakes...they will admit them. They will recognize that they are accountable to others, not just those who are "over" them. People in a healthy organization can fully risk being open with each other due to the high levels of trust (Batcher, 2019). Provides Leadership: Leadership is described as Initiative, Influence, and Impact. Leaders do not neglect to take appropriate action; they have a bias for action. This initiative-taking comes not from being driven by personal ambition but by being called to serve the highest needs of others. Envision the future: Organizations are future-oriented. They look ahead to envision what could be and should be. Leaders recognize that they partner with other leaders looking ahead to the future. This organization shares its vision openly to create a new and shared vision with others (Laub, 2019). Shares Leadership: In these organizations, the leader shares their power with others so that others can lead, thus increasing the potential influence and impact of the total organization. Share the vision; organi-

zations know that an organization's vision does not belong to a single leader. A clear vision of the future, shared by the entire group, becomes a powerful magnet, drawing together the team's resources, skills, and abilities. Share the power; Power has been described as the ability to do...to act. In organizational terms, it represents the ability to make important decisions, allocate resources, and move people and projects forward to make things happen. Shared leadership empowers all people to act for the group's sound and the organization's mission. Share the status: Leadership is not position, status, or prestige. Leaders in healthy organizations resist the strong tendency to accept special perks and privileges of leadership positions. They know that all people throughout the organization need to be affirmed and recognized for their inherent value and for what they contribute to the success of the whole (Laub, 2019). The literature review showed a lack of empirical research regarding servant leadership in the context of the educational system in Jordan. The study's goal is to discover the extent to which teachers perceived the practice of Servant Leadership among school principals in Jordanian educational directorates.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This research study aims to identify teachers' perceived practice of Servant Leadership among school heads and their coping mechanisms to address the said challenges. This would help us understand the challenges teachers experience in dealing with their school heads as servant leaders.

1.2. Research Questions—The study investigates teachers' perceived practice of Servant Leadership among school heads. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of novice teachers regarding the servant leadership style of their school heads?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges emerging from their School Heads?
- (3) What educational insights are drawn from the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Servant Leadership—While traditional leadership generally involves the accumulation and exercise of power by one at the "top of the pyramid," servant leadership is different. The servant leader shares

power, prioritizes others' needs, and helps people develop and perform as highly as possible. Leadership Style- A leadership style is how a leader accomplishes their team's objective by motivating employees to work towards the com-

mon goal and focusing on their well-being. Understanding leadership style is imperative for a team to work together and keep growing while embracing changes. In the study, novice teachers have little or no prior teaching experience in

their first year of teaching. Unless exempted by their principal, novices are required to participate in the Induction and Mentoring Program. They meet weekly with their mentor(s) regarding lesson plans, management, instruction, etc.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The highlights of the study were significant to the following: Teachers are given insight into the experiences and challenges of teachers that other teachers have when it comes to dealing with school head leadership. This would help them prepare as they would know how to solve prob-

lems that may occur while utilizing the approach. Policy/program implementors could use the results of this study to create policies and programs for teachers, allowing them to help teachers better implement teaching and learning. Lastly, this research would help other researchers if they wish to conduct a similar or comparative study.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research is highly anchored on the theory of the magnum opus of Robert Greenleaf, Servant Leadership, a recent theory of leadership that argues that the most effective leaders are servants of their people. Servant leaders get results for their organization through whole-hearted attention to their followers and followers' needs. Unlike many approaches to leadership, which offer suggestions on how top-level leaders can influence and motivate those further down the hierarchy, servant leadership emphasizes collaboration, trust, empathy, and ethics. The leader should be a servant first, leading from a desire to serve others better and not to attain more power. The assumption is that if leaders focus on the needs and desires of followers, followers would reciprocate through increased teamwork, deeper engagement, and better performance. Greenleaf presented the theory in a 1970 essay, "The Servant as Leader." However, numerous other theorists have contributed to our understanding of servant leadership. One theorist, Larry Spears, outlined ten characteristics of servant leaders by analyzing the writings of Greenleaf. These ten characteristics are listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptu-

alization, foresight, stewardship, commitment to the growth of others, and building community. Servant leadership is one of the more popular theories, especially among Christian leaders who vigorously cite Jesus as the penultimate example of servant leadership. However, its effectiveness in organizations is still being debated. Many researchers and theorists argue that servant leaders can become so focused on the needs of their followers that the needs of the organization suffer as a result. In any case, Servant leadership theory has a place within the spectrum of leadership theory, as it represents the most substantial emphasis on followers of any theory. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected variables. The Experiences of teachers to a servant type of leadership, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice, would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. There is a real concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; how-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ever, the center of the two circles determines that there is a connection between exploring the experiences of teachers when it comes to the servant leadership approach is important to the improvement of teaching and learning process for the curriculum.

2. Methodology

This chapter would introduce the methods that was used in conducting the study and the gathering of data. This also includes the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, data collection, research instrument, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) was optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosoph- ical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – is undertaken with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Decent study task jumps with the range of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the

paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm is the patterning of the thinking of a person; it is a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an act of submitting to a view (Stanage 2007). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who define a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, 'ultimates,' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy.

Ontology This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of the teachers from Catalunan Grande Elementary School, Talomo A District, Davao City Division, were gathered through an in-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping strategies were extracted from the participants. The researcher's inquisitiveness on the experiences of the School Heads became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the BE coordinators so that, as

the research situation. Thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, realities on the implementation of the curriculum in the past and the present are discussed by the participants and tries to look into their ways in coping with the implementation in the new normal. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed.

David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of

the participants would provide highlights as to how the program was implemented before COVID-19 and the present execution of the program.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The phenomenological design describes the interpretations of the participants from their experiences. The participants were required to respond to the questions provided to them via Google Forms. Afterward, they were requested to participate in a Focus Group Discussion virtually and face to face, depending on the situation. At the end of this study, themes and common patterns were extracted from their responses (JamonCaban, 2019). They decided to use a qualitative phenomenological research design because they would dwell on the individual experiences of the teachers under the new normal in Philippine public education. There were 10 school heads as study participants with first-hand experiences with the new normal in Philippine public education. The data gathered were recorded, transcribed, and validated to extract first-hand experiences on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the new normal in Philippine public education from the secondary teachers' lived experiences. The Colaizzi method of data analysis was used in a phenomenological research design. This is purely academic. The participants signed the informed consent, and this study has no risk. They can withdraw anytime as a participant in the study. Ethical considerations and safety health protocols were followed. A phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data is then read, reread, and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

2.4. Research Participants—Purposive sampling was applied to the selection of the research participants. Purposive sampling was a technique in which the researcher relied on judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include public school teachers, either male or female, in Catalunan Grande Elementary School, Talomo A District, in the Division of Davao City. Nine informants were part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, coding was used to protect the participants' identities. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT10 was used for the informants of the in-depth interview. The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants

to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the explored experiences are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas reliving past experiences may be difficult on other occasions. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, the researcher would deal with former teachers in public schools. To ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher would be responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants were highly considered. Besides, they would not be forced to be part of the study when they would refuse. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases can protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants were allowed to ask the researcher questions about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information is transparent to the participants. Moreover, the participants' data gathering and participation were guided by the Informed Consent Form, which the chosen participants signed. Lastly, the results and findings were presented to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested

by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. After gathering the needed data, the researcher transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments are more important to be studied in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions in dealing with the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003).

and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This would allow the participants to amend or remove any information that might identify them. The researcher would reserve the right to employ pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Social Value The study's value to society lies in its focus on elementary teachers. It specifically examines the link between a collaborative support system, teacher motivation, and the crucial area of student digital text reading and comprehension influenced by teacher efficacy. This research could inform policy and program development, ultimately benefiting learners. The researcher prioritizes social value, recognizing the potential for a positive impact on society or individuals as a core ethical principle. To protect research participants, the study will adhere to ethical guidelines. This includes ensuring anonymity, avoiding collecting personally identifiable data, and safeguarding participant identities throughout the research process. *Informed Consent* The study will begin with obtaining written informed consent from participants. The researcher will clearly explain the study's purpose: to understand factors influencing teachers' satisfaction with school clinic services and improve them. Participation is entirely voluntary, and respondents can withdraw without penalty. The researcher will prioritize the respondents' psychological well-being and ensure they have

sufficient information to make an informed decision. Privacy and Confidentiality Participant safety is ensured throughout the survey and interview process, including distribution in a safe environment and administration at their convenience. To protect privacy and confidentiality, the study employs pseudonyms for each participant. We are fully compliant with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. To ensure confidentiality, The researcher will ensure that no personal data is shared without the respondents' consent. To further protect the participants, access to the data will be limited to the researcher alone. The utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were considered to avoid a conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and biased representation of primary data findings must be avoided. The transcripts of the statements are given to the participants for confirmation.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety The researcher would fully disclose the nature of the study to the respondents, explaining its purpose, benefits, and the confidentiality of their responses as outlined in the survey. Respondents will be free to ask any questions related to the study, and the researcher will ensure that no harm comes to them. The questionnaire and interview guide will be designed to avoid offensive or inappropriate content. The study will focus solely on academic information, with no personal data being requested. Respondents will have ample time to complete the survey online. They will be free to skip any questions that may cause psychological or emotional distress or withdraw from the study at any point. The researcher will prioritize their well-being and value their participation. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents are provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or

panel members if they have queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they will not be compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher will ensure the respondents are safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire is distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This are done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Adequacy of Facilities The researcher would strive to complete the study successfully at the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed at the target time.

Community Involvement The researcher would respect the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher would express great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the study.

Justice

To maintain equitable selection, the researcher will implement a non-biased approach, choosing only qualified permanent, regular teachers from the participating schools. Respon-

dent time will be valued by minimizing disruptions to their schedules. As a token of appreciation, each participant will receive a safely delivered package of gratitude containing a small souvenir. The research process began by informing respondents about my role as the researcher and their role as participants in data collection. We emphasized the importance of honest and truthful responses to all survey questions and in any communication related to the study. Participants were also informed that they would be among the first to benefit from the study's findings.

Transparency

Participant welfare will be prioritized through honest and transparent communication. The research methods outlined in this study will be rigorously followed, and supporting data analysis documents will be provided. The researcher will clearly define participant involvement and maintain objectivity in the analysis and presentation of results.

The study's findings will be made accessible to participants and parents. They can obtain

2.6. Role of the Researcher—Qualification of the Researcher The researcher would ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before the-

*2.7. Data Collection—*According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection

the results by requesting a CD copy from the researcher. Sharing the results highlights the study's importance and potential benefits for participants and their families. Participants are informed of their rights: they can withdraw their data at any point before the end of data collection. They can review their interview transcripts to correct or remove identifying information. To ensure participant confidentiality, the researcher will utilize pseudonyms and may alter names and/or non-essential dates when analyzing and reporting the data.

Plagiarism And Fabrication As The Researcher The researcher would respect other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty is present in working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and/or making up of data and/or results were included or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

sis writing, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion.

approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she would

store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In gathering data, strict compliance with IATF protocols was observed. The researcher secured a letter of permission to the participants and send it via email. Upon approval, the researcher used the forms of data collection as prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, recording an in-depth interview and focus group discussion has been used. The researcher needs to get the subjective interaction between the participants of the study. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording) and the interpretive paradigm was used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing and observation and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to collaboratively construct a meaningful reality. Yin as cited by Aquilam (2014) suggested numerous forms of data collection, as follows: documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To have legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers' experiences with the new standard way of teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The interview aimed to gather information on the feelings and experi-

ences of teachers. The participants have been encouraged to express their answers in their most comfortable manner. The interview with the participants has been transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored to be easily found and protected from damage and loss. Furthermore, Interviews has also strengths and weaknesses. One of the strengths of an interview is that the interviews provide helpful information when participants cannot be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They can also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions would encourage unbiased and truthful answers. However, one of the weaknesses is that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer is interpreting the information. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that would please the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require a high level of technical competence. It can be time-consuming, and inexperienced interviewers may be unable to keep the questions suitably focused (Quad, 2016).

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a complete description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This was an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus could be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the

topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experi-

rienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both textual and structural descriptions. This passage is

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006), qualitative data analysis methods fall into two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods that were situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are, therefore, very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which, through its theoretical freedom, “provides a flexible and useful research tool that can potentially provide a rich and detailed yet complex account of data” (Braun Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis.

the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step is data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used thematic grids and charts, the framework technique developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was helpful to me in coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was instrumental in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with code being the most essential segment of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub-themes;

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Phase 5. I defined and named themes, ensuring they gave the reader an immediate sense of the theme. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes) and used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments about the research question.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is vital because the results and findings depend on the researcher’s conduct. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required.

Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibil-

ity Contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the credibility issue, interview as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation.

Transferability Concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating that the results of the work at hand can be applied to a broader population since the findings of a qualitative project were specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It was impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it was my responsibility as a researcher to ensure sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork sites to enable

the reader to make such a transfer.

Confirmability Associated with objectivity in science was the use of instruments not dependent on human skill and perception. However, it was difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases was inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings are the result of the participants' experiences and ideas rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher.

Dependability Involves participants' evaluation of the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of the study such that all are supported by the data received from participants. Confirmability: The degree to which other researchers could confirm the research study's findings.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presents themes that emerged from the analysis, along with comprehensive discussions that answer the study's objectives. Before I began my discussion, I established the symbols I used as I presented the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. I used pseudonyms to refer to the participants in the transcriptions of the interviews.

3.1. Experiences of Novice Teachers on the Servant Leadership Style of the School Head —

3.1.1. Empowered to Grow Professionally—Novice teachers can be empowered to grow professionally through various strategies and support systems. Facilitating networking opportunities for novice teachers with educators from other schools, districts, or professional organizations can broaden their perspectives and expose them to diverse teaching practices and educational resources. Collaboration and networking enhance professional growth by fostering connections and promoting the exchange of ideas. School administrators and mentors can empower novice teachers by implementing

some strategies and support systems, providing them with the necessary tools, experiences, and support to grow professionally and become effective educators. The statement of the participants above shared that because of the Servant Leadership style of the school head, the teachers are empowered to grow professionally with the guidance of the school head. As teachers or teacher educators, many of us entered the profession to make a difference. We had a moral purpose. For me, that moral purpose was and continues to be about inclusion and enabling all learners to participate actively in our schools, communities, and broader society. This involves

focusing on learners' strengths and engaging them in learning that is meaningful to them in their context. However, this is often at odds with values at a system level where education can be seen in a reductionist manner primarily focused on improving outcomes and standards to enhance the knowledge economy. We have seen this emphasis on education for the knowledge economy globally, with several countries competing for one of the top places on internationally benchmarked assessments such as PISA (Sellar Lingard, 2013). This striving for competitive advantage is reflected in the plethora of education policies focused on school improvement to raise literacy, numeracy, and science standards with comparative lip service afforded to issues of equity and inclusion despite increasingly diverse classrooms and rising poverty and homelessness in many countries. So, how do we empower our teachers and educators to stay close to their moral purpose; how can we challenge the status quo when the system seems to be at odds with our values and beliefs? This dissonance can lead to a professional identity crisis for teachers and educators, resulting in what Jack Whitehead (Citation1989) termed a 'living contradiction.' Resolving this arguably forms part of our ethical code as professionals and becomes part of our professional identity. Central to this endeavor for me was and continues to be professional learning. Professional learning has empowered me to stay close to my moral purpose for teaching and learning. It has enabled me to have challenging and courageous conversations about teaching and learning and helped me articulate my values and beliefs around the purpose of education. Professional learning enabled me to become aware of my positionality in terms of how my values and beliefs intersect with the wider professional and political contexts at the various levels of the system (Forde and Torrance Citation2017). In turn, this has empowered me to find ways to use my agency to make changes to align my values and practice. Noteworthy is that this has been a collective endeavor requiring a focus not only on developing my own human capital but also social capital. This is particularly important in the context of inclusion, which requires social learning processes to influence attitudes, beliefs, and practices (Ainscow Sandill, 2010). Collaborative models of professional learning and dialogue are central to this endeavor. However, teachers and teacher educators continue to struggle to find the time and space for 'critical conversations' (Ryan, 2014) and 'complicated discussions' (Lopez, 2014) despite critical dialogue being seen as one of the most important pedagogies of effective teacher learning (Parker et al. Citation2016). This is hardly surprising given that the system, through its various policies, promotes competition over cooperation and, in many countries, judges individual teacher performance through a high-stakes accountability agenda. However, the articles on this issue may help us navigate this complex terrain through discussions of the challenging issues and suggestions for ways forward. Teacher empowerment has been analyzed and discussed in the literature for several decades (Bogler and Somech, 2004[]). It has been described as the process through which teachers, as other members of the school, "develop the competence to take charge of their growth" and to face the challenges in their daily practice (Short 2014[]). It stands for teachers believing they have what is necessary to affect their work environment (Short Greer, 2019). The belief in one's empowerment goes hand in hand with the ability to exercise that influence. This is a teacher agency. Agency is a feature of teachers' engagement with their peers and their environment and the scope they have in defining those relations (Biesta, Priestley, and Robinson, 2015). Empowered teachers are professionals who are able to exercise agency. Teachers' empowerment and agency can take many forms. What is central is the extent to which teachers' working envi-

ronments allow them enough voice, autonomy, and confidence through collaboration channels, active roles in collective decision-making, and suitable combinations of support, motivation, and autonomy. It will explore several dimensions of principals' autonomy and autonomy transfers to teachers and their instructional and distributed leadership. It will analyze teachers' empowerment and agency through the perception of autonomy, their feelings of self-efficacy, and collaboration's place in their professional practice. Finally, while traditional mechanisms of empowerment may be in place, some factors can hinder the actual development of the agency. For this reason, the chapter will explore the perceptions of school principals and teachers on how resource shortages can be a barrier to teachers delivering educational goals. School autonomy has been identified as a strong lever for empowering school leaders and teachers (OECD, 2020). This section reports on the share of principals with significant responsibilities for school-level decisions and tasks. As noted in previous TALIS reports (OECD, 2020), when it comes to school autonomy across education levels, school principals usually report more autonomy as the level of education increases. The share of principals that reported significant responsibilities for school-level decisions and

3.1.2. Strong Communication—Assertive communication is crucial for perceiving the practice of servant leadership among school heads. Open and Transparent Communication: School heads who practice servant leadership cultivate an environment of open and transparent communication. They actively listen to the concerns, ideas, and feedback of their staff, students, and parents. By fostering a culture of open communication, school heads create opportunities for others to share their perspectives, feel heard, and actively participate in decision-making processes. Based on the responses above, Servant leadership remains one

tasks reflects this relative increase in school autonomy across education levels. Advocates for school autonomy consider that local authorities, as well as school governing boards and principals, have better knowledge of their limitations and needs, and they can manage more efficiently than other centralized instances of administration (Caldwell Spinks, 2013). While school autonomy does seem to affect better efficacy in improving educational outcomes (Eskeland Filmer, 2002), the actual impact is not uniform across systems (Galiani, Gertler, and Schargrodsky, 2008). Evidence suggests that strong institutional support and suitable accountability mechanisms allow for strong school decision-making based on local knowledge. This results in better resource allocation and improved school performance (Elacqua et al., 2021). However, school autonomy is by no means absolute. It often involves multiple authorities and stakeholders participating in the decision-making processes (OECD, 2020[6]). The great majority of school-level decision-making is usually restricted by national or supranational regulations (e.g., national regulations on teachers' salaries and salary scales, regulations on teachers' minimum qualifications and/or training to enter the teaching profession). It is also routinely scrutinized by different authorities (OECD, 2020).

of the most effective models of leadership today. School principals who embody this leadership paradigm encourage and enable teachers and demonstrate a desire to build school community. Teachers' effectiveness increases as they are honored and served by their principal, positively impacting students, colleagues, and parents. Servant leaders often put the organization's needs ahead of personal needs and honor people, not programs and politics. Students ultimately benefit from this leadership approach as their teachers learn to serve them first as people and then confidently lead them into their learning. Principals who model ser-

vant leadership increase teacher effectiveness in their schools. Principals must understand the servant leadership role of modeling a servant's heart, enabling teachers to act in encouraging teachers' hearts (Grothaus, 2004), and communicating a larger vision in order to optimize the paradigm of servant leadership. Servant leadership increases teacher effectiveness by positively impacting their personal beliefs and values, interactions with colleagues (Crippen, 2010; Taylor et al., 2007), classroom leadership, interactions with students, and desire and ability to build a school community (Crippen, 2012). The definition of servant leadership and the associated personal characteristics will be established, and false notions of it will be revealed so that a comprehensible perspective can be maintained throughout this paper. Servant leadership is multi-dimensional and requires deep understanding for more principals to acknowledge its potential to increase teacher effectiveness, change schools, and meet organizational needs (Taylor et al., 2007). Servant leadership starts with desire. Stewart (2012) agreed with Robert Greenleaf's original notion of servant leadership in the 1970s, which highlighted the intrinsic feeling of leaders wanting to serve. That selfless desire to serve (Herman Marlowe) establishes servant leaders as servants first, and leaders second. A leader's greatness is built upon the practice of serving other people (Spears, 2004), and although servant leaders are servants first, they can be great leaders because "leading and serving are two sides of the same coin" (Sultan van de Bunt-Kokhuis, 2014). The essential skills, knowledge, and character traits that are consistently understood as leadership

staples are still required to lead people (Buskey, 2014); the difference becomes apparent in the leader's value system based on the leader's actions and interactions with people. Servant leaders genuinely care about people and will sacrificially serve and focus on their followers' needs (Taylor et al., 2007). Leaders are often developed and discovered by those acts of service and stewardship. Servant leaders go beyond meeting the needs of individuals in the organization and put aside personal desires to meet the needs of the organization (Taylor et al., 2007). Cerit (2009) believed that the practice of servant leadership is embedded in the understanding that the leader's self-interest comes second to the good of those being led. Servant leadership can be defined "as an attitude of leading others from a perspective of placing the organizational purpose, the needs of the organization, and the needs of people over the needs and desire of the leader" (Herman Marlowe, 2005, p. 601), and as "an action-oriented state of mind that compels leaders to provide followers with what the followers need in order that the followers might be able to do what needs to be done" (Taylor et al., 2007, p. 405). Hansel (1987) defined a servant leader with more of a balance between the "servant" and the "leader" portions by emphasizing the leader's vision, skill, and creativity and the servant's values, attitudes, and heart. Whichever way a servant leader is defined on paper, he or she consistently transforms people and organizations (Crippen, 2012; Spears, 2004; Sultan van de Bunt-Kokhuis, 2014) and creates compelling, growing, healthy communities (Crippen, 2010) in schools today.

3.2. *Coping Mechanism With The Challenges Emerging From Their School Head* — Another objective of this study is to explore the different coping mechanisms teachers employ

to address the challenges emerging from their School Heads. From the interviews, the teachers shared that the coping mechanisms they employ are practicing mindfulness and seeking support from others.

Fig. 3. Experiences Of Novice Teachers On The Servant Leadership Style Of Their School Heads

3.2.1. *Practice Mindfulness*—Teachers focus on being intensely aware of what they sense and feel for a specific time without interpretation or judgment. Caring professions such as teaching are often associated with burnout and emotional exhaustion. Teachers are often required to problem-solve and provide pastoral care, addressing varied and complex emotional situations. Increased accountability, work intensification, the extension of the working day into personal time, and student behavior concerns can also challenge teacher well-being. The interpersonal nature of teaching can result in a high degree of social-emotional labor, where teachers need to regulate their emotions with others. These social emotions, combined with a high workload, can be emotionally taxing and result in burnout due to work-related stress (McCallum Price, 2010). A growing body of research focuses on teacher wellbeing and addressing work-related stress and burnout. In a pre-COVID study of Australian teachers (N = 749), the findings indicated that 55%

The COVID-19 pandemic has seriously affected education systems worldwide, from early childhood education (e.g., Eadie et al., 2021) to secondary and primary sectors (see Reimers, 2022). It was expected that educators would seamlessly shift to remote teaching (Lambert Schuck, 2021). In reality, the rapid change to learning remotely during lockdown resulted in emergency remote teaching rather than online learning. When periods of emergency remote teaching are required, the responsibility shifts to the teachers with minimal support provided by the Information Technology teams, which would occur when online learning is prepared and developed (Azevedo et al., 2020; Hodges et al., 2020). In an online survey of teachers from Australia (n = 2,373) and New Zealand (n = 1,183) in April 2020, teachers raised concerns with unfamiliar teaching methods and technologies (e.g., Zoom and Skype), isolation from colleagues and students and fears for their students' psychological welfare (Flack et al., 2020). The teachers shared that they had lost confidence in their

ability to cater to 30 students in a virtual classroom, as well as less connection with their students. A teacher's well-being depends on the circumstances, school environment, and psychological, cognitive, and emotional resources (Day and Oing, 2009). The contextual factors, including the school and classroom context, influence a teacher's job satisfaction, work-related stress, and intent to leave the profession (Travers, 2017). Relationships with students are ranked as one of the important sources of enjoyment and motivation for teachers (Spilt et al., 2011). However, dealing with misbehavior and disciplining students is repeatedly reported as a teacher stressor (Skaalvik Skaalvik, 2010; Lambert et al., 2015; McCarthy, 2019). Student behaviors influence job satisfaction and the intent to leave the profession, as experienced by teachers (Skaalvik Skaalvik, 2010; Hughes, 2012; Liu Onwuegbuzie, 2014). A positive teacher-student interaction creates a classroom environment where students feel safe, valued, and supported, reducing disruptive behavior and disciplinary measures (Roeser et al., 2013). A teacher's social-emotional competence and general well-being influence the classroom environment they create, how students learn, behavior management strategies implemented, and ultimately, student's social, emotional, and academic outcomes (Flook et al., 2013). As McCallum and Price (2010) identified, teachers must be well themselves to positively impact their students' wellbeing. Motivated, engaged teachers positively impact student behavior and student-teacher interactions. Teacher well-being is seen to indirectly impact students' socioemotional adjustment and academic performance (Spilt et al., 2011). It is argued that improved health and well-being among teachers through the inclusion of mindfulness-based interventions lead to greater occupational engagement and job satisfaction, lower rates of burnout, absenteeism, and intent to leave the profession (Jennings, 2011; Soloway et al., 2011; Flook et

al., 2013; Skinner Beers, 2016). Teachers are at the heart of creating supportive learning environments for students, and they need to be equipped with the skills to care for themselves and their students (Howard Johnson, 2004; Lindqvist et al., 2017). Mindfulness research and applications are steadily increasing in school settings. According to Shapiro and Carlson (2009), "Mindfulness is the awareness that arises through intentionally attending in an open, accepting, and discerning way to whatever is arising in the present moment" (Shapiro Carlson, 2009, p. 124). The components of mindfulness include focusing on the present moment, non-judgmental acceptance of experiences and events, and the ability to control negative emotions (Coffey, Hartman, Fredrickson, 2010). Research has shown that when people are mindful, they are not distracted by external or internal stimuli and are better able to pay attention to tasks (Napoli, Krech, Holley, 2005). Mindfulness also enables individuals to regulate negative emotions in stressful situations (Beddoe Murphy, 2004). Additionally, mindful people are believed to have increased cognitive ability and concentration under pressure (2004). 2 As indicated by the publication of recent studies, there is a growing interest in the impact of mindfulness training for teachers. While some studies are based on other training formats or apply meditation techniques that are possibly not comparable to mindfulness meditation (Anderson, Levinson, Barker, Kiewra, 1999), the studies reviewed here use Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBRS) training for teachers. As educators deal with the world's increasing complexity and uncertainty, it is important to have an outlet that will help maintain mental health as well as help promote job satisfaction. Mindfulness may be one such outlet, as it has been proven effective, resilient, and low-cost response to seemingly obstinate problems (Kagan, 1992). Besides the health benefits, mindfulness is free, and everyone can

be present while not having to change oneself to meet criteria (Hargreaves, 1998). Moreover, those who practice mindfulness could potentially cultivate innate qualities with simple practices that are scientifically demonstrated to benefit oneself, loved ones, friends, neighbors, colleagues, institutions, and organizations (Hargreaves, 1998). This literature review covers mindfulness and the theoretical framework (Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory). The literature review explores the history and explanation of mindfulness as well as its benefits. A review of research related to depression, anxiety, stress, and job satisfaction is presented, as well as the implications of incorporating job-embedded professional development for educators. Mindfulness decreases stress, enhances performance, and helps participants gain insight and awareness through observing one's mind (Parsons et al., 2017). By practicing mindfulness, one typically shows an increase in attention to others' well-being (Parsons et al., 2017). Both science and experience demonstrate positive benefits for health, happiness, work, and relationships (Kagan, 2012). Mindfulness is available to everyone in every moment, whether through meditation or mindful moment practices like taking time to pause and breathe when overwhelmed (Kabat-Zinn, 2018). The following sections will define mindfulness, outline the historical development of mindfulness, and provide an overview of mindfulness practice. What is Mindfulness? Mindfulness is the ability to pay specific attention to the present moment nonjudgmentally (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). Brown, Ryan, and Creswell (2007) described mindful awareness as a "foundation for healthy self-regulation." A recent review of the neuroscience of mindfulness suggests that the practice of mindfulness may impact self-regulation by improving the regulation of attention and emotions (Tang, Hölzel, Posner, 2015). Originally a Buddhist concept, mindful awareness describes a generic psychological faculty (Thera, 2015). It

may be directed to bodily sensations and emotional and cognitive experiences. Mindfulness is a practice involved in various religious and secular traditions, from Hinduism and Buddhism to yoga and, more recently, non-religious meditation (Chakalson, 2014). Today, Buddhism is most often thought of by non-practitioners in terms of Tibetan Buddhism and the Dalai Lama, an individual thought to be an enlightened teacher of Tibetan Buddhism (Parsons et al., 2017). Because mindfulness is more involved in Buddhism than Hinduism, mindfulness is considered the first step to enlightenment reached by the Buddhist practice of meditation to bring about a state of ultimate consciousness, thus allowing personal attunement with a higher purpose in life (Parsons et al., 2017). Some believe the English term "mindfulness" is a simple translation of the Buddhist concept of Sati, which means awareness (Parsons et al., 2017). People have practiced mindfulness for thousands of years, whether on their own or as part of a larger tradition (Thera, 1975). Mindfulness was popularized at least 2,500 years ago in the East through religious and spiritual institutions (Khoury et al., 2013). Most Western practitioners and teachers of mindfulness learned about such practices in the Buddhist tradition through Tibetan Buddhism and the Dalai Lama; an individual is thought to be an enlightened teacher of Tibetan Buddhism who escaped to India in 1956 during the Tibetan uprising (Khoury et al., 2013). Other religions also have mindfulness roots (Khoury et al., 2013). The following sections will detail ancient mindfulness and describe standard modern mindfulness programs. Ancient Mindfulness. Many think that mindfulness practice lies in Buddhism; however, the history of mindfulness goes further back to yoga practices of the Hindu people dated to 2300 BC and 1500 BC in the Indus Valley, near modern day Pakistan (Thera, 1975). In fact, Hindu scripture has many references to meditation, silence, and acceptance, which are all impor-

tant elements of modern mindfulness (Hacker Davis, 2006). Hinduism and Buddhism share many commonalities, such as they both formed in the same region and are greatly concerned with the concept of living in harmony with the natural order of the universe (Hacker Davis, 2006); However, Buddhism is a religion and a philosophy that aims to show its followers the path to enlightenment, which means free from misinformation (Tang, Hölzel, Posner, 2015). Buddhism was founded around 400-500 BC by Siddhartha Gautama, who became referred to as Buddha (Hacker Davis, 2006). Gautama is thought to have been born and raised around modern-day India and Nepal (Hacker Davis, 2006). Based on where and 13 when Gautama was raised, it is thought that Hinduism informed his upbringing (Khoury et al., 2013). Since Buddha's death, Buddhism has split into Theravada Buddhism and Zen Buddhism (Parsons et al., 2017). The next section will bridge the gap between ancient mindfulness and mindfulness practices in Christianity and Islam. Mindful Practices in Christianity and Islam. Although mostly influenced by Hinduism and Buddhism, the history of mindfulness goes beyond these two practices. Mindfulness also has roots in Judaism, Christianity, and Islam (Trousselard et

al., 2014). In Christianity, Jesus speaks of the innermost I am, referring to the essence of every lifeform, also known as Christ within (Tolle, 1999). Another well-known example in Christianity is Brother Lawrence, who emphasized being aware of the "Holy Spirit" in Practicing the Presence of God (Lawrence, 2004). Islam also emphasizes mindfulness as seen in "Muraqabah," or better known as having a continuous awareness as Allah is always watching (Al-Jawziyyah, 2016). The basic mindfulness in Islam is that there is a pure core (the Fitrah) within everyone as every child is born with the Fitrah regardless of caste, creed, and religion (Al-Jawziyyah, 2016). Thus, Muslims access this purity through the practices of mindfulness (Lawrence, 2004). Next, mindfulness popularity will be described as it moves to the West. Mindfulness Popularity to the West. Thich Nhat Hahn, a Vietnamese Zen master, was one of the first to bring mindfulness to popularity in the West in the mid-1970s (Hacker Davis, 2006). He introduced simple yet profound teachings on mindful practices in daily life (Hacker Davis, 2006). His book *The Miracle of Mindfulness* has been used by generations of Buddhist and non-Buddhist practitioners in modern times (Parsons et al., 2017).

3.2.2. *Seek Support from Others*—Another coping method used by novice teachers is seeking support from others. Participants agree that in order to maintain the continuity in the operations of the school, they should have a support for each other. The first years of teaching are a period of intense transition as novice teachers take on the responsibilities of planning instruction, teaching, assessing students, and managing a classroom while also encountering "incompatible notions of the best means by which to teach. The student-centered theories and pedagogical approaches novice teachers have studied in their teacher preparation programs are often incon-

gruent with the prescriptive and standardized institutional norms (Ravitch, 2010) in the schools in the United States. Smagorinsky et al. (2015) argued that "this conundrum helps explain why beginning teachers experience such dissonance when moving between universities and schools. When trying to develop a conception of practical instruction for themselves. This article reports findings from a study of a year-long professional development program that we implemented as part of our efforts to provide support for novice teachers that could help them learn to adapt to the affordances and constraints of their instructional and institutional contexts. In

particular, the authors draw upon findings from this study to address the pressing need for professional development programs that respond to the challenges novice teachers encounter in their specific teaching contexts. The professional development program was designed to create opportunities for novice teachers to examine the kinds of challenges they encounter and provide a mechanism that might help them explore and learn from the underlying sources of tension within those struggles. We studied the implementation of this program to generate understandings that can inform efforts to re-imagine and improve the systems of support currently available for novice teachers. Our study of the implementation of this professional development program was guided by the following question: What kinds of challenges do novice teachers encounter and how might exploring those challenges in structured dialogue designed to position struggle as a source of growth inform approaches to professional development? We will discuss what we learned about the challenges novice teachers participating in this study encountered and their responses to them. We use that discussion to articulate the nuances within those challenges the data indexed in relation to the act of teaching and occupying the role of teacher in order to present recommendations for improving professional development programs. The Participant who was in his third year of teaching at the time of this study, gave voice to one significant challenge he encountered related to the disconnect between the beliefs that informed his conceptions of teaching and the reality of his teaching context. He shared his struggle to reconcile his notions of what teaching would be with the reality he encountered with the other participants in this study by saying: So, coming out of college, I had all these grandiose ideas. These big ideas are what I wanted to achieve in my students' learning. I had a really hard time transitioning into the actual classroom. concerns echo those

voiced by other novice teachers who have become frustrated by a disconnect between who they want to be as teachers and what is required of them by their teaching contexts (Barnes, 2018; Smagorinsky et al., 2004). A study by Fecho et al. (2021) highlighted the frustration that can occur as novice teachers experience conflict between their pedagogical goals and their teaching contexts. Elise, for example, wanted to be a teacher who could bring “content into dialogue with students’ lives. Working from this stance, Elise had created a unit of instruction on Romeo Juliet designed “to lead her students in an exploration of how Shakespeare created characters and conflict. It is believed the characters and the conflicts in this play would resonate with the personal experiences of the adolescent readers in her classroom. However, the pacing guide her school required her to follow constrained her ability to leverage those connections because it only allowed seven 90-minute class periods to read this complex play. Elise felt she had to “rush through the text. Without enough time to explore the play in the depth she felt was necessary, Elise became frustrated by what she deemed as her “failure to connect such a connect-able play in a dialogical way. Our previous research in teacher education and teacher induction (Stewart, 2018; Stewart et al., 2019; Stewart Jansky, 2021) indicates that professional development approaches that explore the specific challenges that novice teachers encounter in their classrooms can help them develop novel ways to respond to those challenges. Findings from each of these studies pointed to the ways in which engaging in collaborative dialogue that explored the participants’ specific contextual challenges enabled them to work together to posit productive responses to struggle that increased their senses of agency and confidence. As schools in the United States become increasingly prescriptive and standardized () novice teachers encounter challenges that can undermine their confidence and create

dissonance because the prevailing instructional norms and policies in schools grind against their pedagogical orientations (e. g. Smagorinsky et al., 2015). As Stewart et al. (2020) reported from their study of the challenges teacher candidates encounter during their student teaching experiences, the dissonance between the theories they studied in their teacher preparation program and the policies and prevailing pedagogical approaches they were expected to carry out in the field can cause them to question their ability to succeed in the profession, which contributes to the alarming problem of teacher attrition (Strong, 2016). Professional development programs have the potential to provide crucial support that enables novice teachers to critically reflect on their pedagogical orientations and the instructional approaches they believe will be effective and find pathways to success—even amid struggle (Luekens et al., 2005;). To provide such support, however, professional development programs must be sustained and focused “on the problems that teachers encounter in their daily work” (Gibbons Cobb, 2017). Research indicates that it is imperative to provide teachers with effective professional development during their first five years in the profession (Stewart, et al., 2019). Despite a long history of arguments that sustainable, effective professional development is a significant factor in novice teacher support and reducing teacher attrition rates (Dunn et al., 2019), the kinds and amounts of professional development or induction support that novice teachers receive as they enter the profession can be described—at best—as uneven or unpredictable (Ingersoll, 2012; Izadinia, 2016; Kidd et al., 2015; Mitchell et al., 2020). Induction programs for new teachers that formally pair novice teachers with experienced mentors are commonplace in U.S. schools (Chu, 2019; Gordon 2017). Providing a novice teacher with a supportive mentor can be, as Izadinia (2015) argued, an invaluable source of “encouragement and emotional backing” (p. 398). However, such pairings alone do not guarantee growth or success because “the personalities, abilities, and persona of teachers vary widely” (Gay, 1995, p. 104). Differing pedagogical goals and divergent perspectives on effective approaches to instruction can undermine the success of these mentoring partnerships because a “technique that works well for one individual in a particular time and place may not work equally well for someone else, or even the same person when the context changes” (p. 104). For example, a veteran teacher who values an orderly, quiet classroom and has successfully engaged students and supported their learning by leaning heavily on lecture might struggle to provide effective guidance for a novice teacher whose teacher education program focused on student-centered approaches to instruction, such as discussions that can appear chaotic when that veteran teacher is walking by the classroom or dropping in for an ad-hoc observation. Trevor had such an experience with Mr. Thomas, who was the veteran teacher assigned to mentor him during his first year as a high school English teacher. Mr. Thomas was universally respected by the faculty and the students. He was also a committed, supportive mentor. However, Mr. Thomas had spent his career teaching from pedagogical stance that stood in stark contrast to Trevor’s student-centered, discussion-heavy approach. The contrast between their pedagogical beliefs and approaches to teaching each day made it difficult for Mr. Thomas to help Trevor respond to the challenges he encountered. While Mr. Thomas could (and often did) offer him useful advice on how to integrate lecture into his lessons, he was not as well equipped to help Trevor learn how improve his ability to manage those moments when a class discussion stayed too far from its intended purpose. It is not always possible to pair novice teachers with mentors who share similar personalities or philosophies of teaching. Nor, we would argue, is such a lack of diversity in thinking productive.

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism With The Challenges Emerging From Their School Head

There is much to be learned from tension and divergent perspectives (Fecho et al., 2021). Thus, it is important to augment formal one-on-one mentoring programs with larger programmatic teacher induction programs that account for the

importance of the developmental and contextual needs of the novice teachers they serve and create conditions in which novice teachers can share their struggles and seek guidance from a range of perspectives, voices, and personalities.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Study—The study’s final goal is to attract conclusions from its findings. These conclusions were drawn from emerging themes in teachers namely, under servant leadership

style, teachers with have also a supportive kind of leadership. Another is having a productive work environment since a good rapport is established between the School Head and the Novice Teachers.

3.3.1. Supportive Leadership—According to Morrison (2012), teachers are leaving faster than they can be replaced and shortages will remain until retention efforts are addressed. While there are numerous factors influencing teacher turnover, this review focuses on Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs theory, the changing role of the principal, and three areas of support that include instructional, school culture, and professional growth. Supportive behaviors prevalent in the literature are discussed. Principals should

focus on them in order to create caring conditions, which will increase teacher retention. Smith and Ingersoll (2004) used the term the revolving door to describe the constant movement of teachers in and out of America’s schools, and considered it to be one of the fundamental causes of inadequate school performance. According to The MetLife Survey of the American Teacher: An Examination of School Leadership (2013), 57Darling-Hammond (2003) emphasized that keeping a good teacher should

be one of the most important agenda items of any school leader because well-prepared and capable teachers have the largest effect on student learning. She suggests that school and district leaders should change policy and practice in order to improve working conditions, which she believes will increase teacher retention. Dr. Richard Ingersoll has been a leading contributor to the study of teacher retention for over a decade; many researchers (Morrison, 2012) have built their studies using his findings. In his report, *The Wrong Solution to the Teacher Shortage*, for the National Commission on Teaching and America's Future (NCTAF),

3.3.2. Productive Work Environment—The work environment of teachers is vital; after all, the working environment of teachers is the learning condition of students, and the unproblematic environment in which to teach is also the comfortable environment in which to learn. High satisfaction and low intention to leave the teaching profession are high among teachers in schools with favourable working conditions, regardless of student demographics and socioeconomic background of the teachers [2]. Schools' organizational characteristics have been the subject of a growing body of research. Despite growing recognition of the critical nature of working conditions, researchers have only recently begun to understand how various aspects of the workplace affect teachers' ability to teach effectively, their sense of self-efficacy, their satisfaction with their role and assignment, and their willingness to remain in their school and profession. Teacher demographics, qualifications, school organizational traits, school resources, and student body characteristics are all factors that influence teacher attrition. Teaching conditions are more important than previously thought in predicting teacher attrition. Working conditions, notably administrative assistance, school amenities, and class size, are far more

he stated that the United States suffers from a teacher turnover crisis, not a teacher shortage (Ingersoll Smith, 2003). Ingersoll (2004) cites several reasons for high rates of attrition including inadequate support from school administrators, too many intrusions upon instructional time, student discipline problems, and limited teacher input into school decisionmaking. High accountability standards placed on today's public schools demand continuity of staff and programs. Without this continuity, educators are unable to create and implement plans that will meet the ever-changing needs of students.

significant to teachers than remuneration and student demographics. Working conditions, in addition to salary and incentives, have a significant impact on teachers' career intentions. Another crucial factor influencing teachers' career choices is school administration, specifically the quality of a school's leadership. The success of any school is depending on seven pivotal issues, "teacher selection, teacher dismissal, evaluation policy, enrolment policy, textbook selection, curriculum content, and curriculum design. However, interpersonal, academic, socioeconomic, political and administrative relationships are all part of educational institutions. In primary and secondary schools, a conglomeration of intellectuals and well-informed individuals hailing from different sociocultural, ethnic, and religious backgrounds come together to pursue a single goal providing education. Like all other organizations, a school is a workplace for teachers, and a specific working environment, as well as the overall arrangement of these specific circumstances, can influence their perspective. Some features of the work environment are essential, but their effects on well-being will vary as to their level increases. These features include (1) opportunity for control; (2) opportunity for skill use; (3) externally generated goals;

(4) variety, (5) environmental clarity; (6) availability of money; (7) physical security, (8) opportunity for interpersonal contact; (9) valued social position. While all of them are important for psychological well-being in moderation, some, like workload, are thought to be damaging to well-being at very high levels. Some other variables, including money and social status, are unlikely to harm well-being even if their level is high. Teachers' self-efficacy is influenced by collective efficacy, school environment, and mastery experiences [12], whereas perceived organizational support can enhance educators' self-esteem by reducing occupational stress [13]. A recent research indicates that excessive workload, bias based on social identity perception, discrimination and favoritism, not receiving help from upper management, feeling unvalued, and financial issues were among the reasons instructors quit school management. Besides, unhappiness and anxiety, feelings of depression, failure and inadequacy, mental exhaustion and depersonalization, anxiety, dilemma, tension, feeling worthless, anxiety, hurt, and apathy were among the emotional states generated by these factors. Recently, an approach was developed to measure the employee's perceptions of an acceptable workplace; such things as effort and commitment to the organization, as well as what they expect in return, like payment, respect, or promotion, were factors in an employee's perception of a healthy workplace. It is believed that a psychological contract exists between employees and employers. If an employee believes their employer has failed to uphold this contract by, for example, not promoting someone based on effort, they will experience stronger negative emotions that can negatively affect their physical and mental health in the long term. When the psychological contract is viewed as fair, psychological well-being is likely to improve. The work environment is characterized in this approach as a set of beliefs held by the employee about how the organiza-

tion will respond to their job activities. Where employees perceive some factors in the work environment as unsatisfying, then such an environment may be construed as being toxic. Hence, for an environment to be perceived as satisfying (conducive), the Person (p)-Environment (E) relationship must be equivalent, such as E should fulfil the requirement. The work environment includes the sum of the interrelationships that exist among the employees and the employers; it reflects the conducive aspects like organizational and supervisory encouragement, workgroup support as well as toxic conditions like insufficient resources, organizational impediments, and work pressure. The basic question the present research deals with is which of the factors do teachers consider as constituting the conducive and the toxic environment of the schools. It may also be of interest to inquire into which of these factors in work environments exert more influence on job commitment. Further, the teachers' skills may develop to where they outgrow their role, or their priorities may shift because of non-work commitments; likewise, the nature of the work environment or the rewards that a school can offer may change over the years. The correspondence between the teacher and the school environment may not be perfect, perhaps because the teacher chose the wrong career or the school administration chose the wrong person; even a good correspondence can deteriorate over time [19]. Hence, it is worthy to outline the relationships between the factors and the year of experiences by the teachers. A variety of factors can affect the physical and psychological well-being of teachers in the work environment. The present research focuses on understanding believed to have a significant impact on teaching. There has been no reliable, valid method for adequately assessing the teachers' percept of their work environment dimensions. Promoting effective teaching for all students, especially those from low-income families, cannot be achieved by merely offering

Fig. 5. Insights Gained from The Results Of The Experiences And Coping Mechanism Of Novice Teachers Under Servant Leadership Style

financial rewards or through compelling teachers to reassign. Good teachers will come and remain, and their pupils will learn if the school is known for being a helpful and productive environment. Besides, the work environment is related to school policies. The administrators of schools need to understand the school's environment to enhance the job commitment of

the teachers and be able to develop policies that are consistent with the academic curriculum. Therefore, empirical probing to answer these questions will serve as a guide for educational policymakers and school administrators to identify which factors in the school environment need urgent attention and modification.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in improving teachers' experiences are also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—This study's objectives were to explore novice teachers' experiences under the servant leadership style and gain insight into the different challenges that teachers experienced under such a leadership style. The study's findings revealed that teachers must practice mindfulness so that they are not over-

whelmed with tasks. Also, to feel at ease in their work, one must seek support from the other. It takes a village to raise a child and a community to have a better working environment. In terms of the experiences, teachers have shared that they were empowered to perform their respective task though they are monitored properly by

the School Head. However, this discipline improves their channel of communication among

teachers and the School Head as well.

4.2. Implications—Several implications can be drawn from the results of this study. The first theme was the experiences of novice teachers with the servant leadership style of their school heads. It was revealed that being empowered to grow professionally and having strong communication skills were the points to consider. Encouraging novice teachers to take on leadership roles within the school community empowers them to grow professionally. This can include leading professional development sessions, participating in curriculum development, serving on committees, or engaging in action research projects. Establishing a constructive feedback and evaluation system is essential for empowering novice teachers. Regular classroom observations, feedback sessions, and evaluations can help identify strengths, address weaknesses, and set goals for improvement. Providing specific and actionable feedback contributes to the professional growth of novice teachers. Next is Strong communication. School heads who practice servant leadership cultivate an environment of open and transparent communication. They actively listen to the concerns, ideas, and feedback of their staff, students, and parents. By fostering a culture of open communication, school heads create opportunities for others to share their perspectives, feel heard, and actively participate in decision-making processes. Effective communication involves conveying clear and consistent messages about the school's vision, mission, and goals. School heads practicing servant leadership articulate their values and expectations to all stakeholders, ensuring everyone understands and aligns with the shared purpose of serving the school community. For the coping mechanisms, themes were revealed as follows: first was practicing mindfulness. A re-

lease mechanism to support mental health and job satisfaction was crucial as educators dealt with the world's growing complexity and uncertainty. One such outlet would be mindfulness, an efficient, durable, and affordable solution to insurmountable difficulties. Besides its health advantages, mindfulness is free, and everyone can be present without altering who they are to fit a specific mold. Additionally, persons who practice mindfulness may develop intrinsic abilities through straightforward techniques scientifically shown to be advantageous for themselves, close relatives, friends, neighbors, coworkers, institutions, and companies. Next is Seek Support from others. The first few years of teaching are a time of intensive change as new instructors learn how to manage a classroom, organize lessons, teach, and assess students. They also meet "incompatible notions of the best ways to teach." The normative and prescribed institutional standards frequently conflict with the student-centered theories and pedagogical practices that beginning teachers have studied in their teacher preparation programs. It was believed that the characters and the conflicts in this play would resonate with the personal experiences of the adolescent readers in her classroom. However, the pacing guides her school required her to follow constrained her ability to leverage those connections because it only allowed seven 90-minute class periods to read this complex play. Elise felt she had to "rush through the text. Without enough time to explore the play in the depth she felt was necessary, Elise became frustrated by what she deemed as her "failure to connect such a connect-able play in a dialogical way. In summary, it was essential to perceive the practice of servant leadership among school heads. Effective communication techniques such as open and transparent

communication, active listening, empathy, two-way communication, trust, authenticity, collaborative decision-making, and recognition con-

tribute to the perception of servant leadership in school leadership practices.

4.3. Future Directions—Future directions for novice teachers in perceiving the practice of servant leadership among school heads can include the following: **Professional Development:** Novice teachers can engage in professional development opportunities focusing on leadership styles, including servant leadership. **Workshops, seminars, and training programs** can help them understand the principles of servant leadership and how it can positively impact their teaching practice and school environment. **Mentorship and Role Models:** Novice teachers could seek mentors or experienced teachers who exemplify servant leadership qualities. By observing and learning from these role models, they can gain practical insights into how servant leadership can be applied in education. **Reflective Practice:** Novice teachers can engage in reflective practice to evaluate and assess the leadership style of their school heads. Through self-reflection, they can identify instances where servant leadership is demonstrated and its impact on the school community. This reflection can help them better understand and appreciate the value of servant leadership. **Collaboration and Feedback:** Novice teachers can actively participate in collaborative discussions and feedback sessions with their school heads. By engaging in open dialogue, they can seek clarification on leadership approaches, express their perceptions, and provide feedback on how servant leadership practices impact their teach-

ing and the overall school environment. **Action Research:** Novice teachers can engage in action research projects that explore and understand servant leadership within their school context. This can involve gathering data and conducting interviews or surveys to examine the perceptions and experiences of various stakeholders regarding servant leadership practices. This research can provide valuable insights for both novice teachers and school heads. **Engage in Leadership Opportunities:** Novice teachers can seek leadership opportunities within the school community. By taking on roles such as department heads, committee members, or team leaders, they can observe and experience servant leadership principles firsthand. These experiences can deepen their understanding of servant leadership and its impact on the school community. **Continuous Learning and Growth:** Novice teachers should prioritize their continuous learning and growth as they strive to become effective educators. By continuously seeking new knowledge, exploring leadership theories, and staying informed about current trends in education, they can better recognize and appreciate the qualities and practices of servant leadership in their school heads. By focusing on these future directions, novice teachers can develop a deeper understanding and appreciation for servant leadership in their school heads. This understanding can positively impact their teaching practice and contribute to creating a supportive and empowering school culture.

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